

New Antitumor Hydroxymethyl Derivatives of Vinblastine

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New hydroxymethyl derivatives (4-6, 9, 15, 16) of the antitumor indole-indoline alkaloids vinblastine and leurosine have been prepared. In addition to the expected 16, the new bisvindoline 17 has been obtained as the main product, as a result of the oxidation reaction.

Vincristine (1) and vinblastine (VLB) (2), the indole-indoline alkaloids of the evergreen *Catharanthus roseus* (Madagascar), have well-known clinical importance in the treatment of cancer¹. In order to prepare new, potentially active or less toxic analogs, we have synthesized some new hydroxymethyl derivatives of VLB (2) and leurosine (LEU) (3), which is another alkaloid of the plant, in two different ways: (i) by conversion of the dimer isolated from the plant and (ii) by the coupling reaction of the monomer alkaloids catharanthine and the corresponding vindoline derivatives.

the methoxycarbonyl group of the vindoline moiety having been reduced and the epoxy and acetyl groups having remained intact. Under thermodynamically controlled conditions, i.e. by refluxing 3 for 2 h, we obtained mainly compound 5, thus the acetyl group has also been hydrolyzed. As an adsorbent for $Zn(BH_4)_2$ charcoal could be used as well.

The analogous hydroxymethyl derivative of VLB, compound 6, was obtained readily by the selective $NaBH_4$ reduction³ of 2 in boiling t-butanol by adding methanol

- 1 $R_1 = OH, R_2 = Et, R_3 = H, R_4 = OAc, R_5 = CHO$
- 2 $R_1 = OH, R_2 = Et, R_3 = H, R_4 = OAc, R_5 = Me$
- 3 $R_1 = Et, R_2, R_3 = O, R_4 = OAc, R_5 = Me$
- 7 $R_1 = OH, R_2 = Et, R_3 = H, R_4 = OH, R_5 = Me$
- 8 $R_1 = OH, R_2 = Et, R_3 = R_4 = H, R_5 = Me$

- 4 $R_1 = Et, R_2, R_3 = O, R_4 = OAc$
- 5 $R_1 = Et, R_2, R_3 = O, R_4 = OH$
- 6 $R_1 = OH, R_2 = Et, R_3 = H, R_4 = OH$
- 9 $R_1 = OH, R_2 = Et, R_3 = R_4 = H$

At first the reduction of LEU (3) was studied. The selective reduction of 3 with $Zn(BH_4)_2$ supported on silica gel² led mainly to one of the two hydroxymethyl derivatives 4 and 5 depending on the specific reaction conditions used. At 40°, after 0.5 h, 4 was the main product with only

dropwise to the reaction mixture. Deacetylvinblastine (7) was isolated as the by-product of this reaction, and 7 could be transformed into 6 by using the above mentioned conditions for $NaBH_4$ reduction. Deacetoxy-VLB (8) was reduced in a similar way resulting in 9.

Some years ago a new and efficient method was discovered to couple the monomer alkaloids catharanthine (10) and vindoline (11) by ferric ion in aqueous acidic media producing 3',4'-anhydrovinblastine^{4a}. Earlier we published MnO₂ oxidation⁵ of vindoline (11) together with the preparation of some new vindoline derivatives, among them that of the *N*-formyl-derivative 12. Usually *N*-formyl vindoline derivatives are not suitable for a coupling reaction, neither by the ferric ion method nor by the well-known Polonovski-Potier method^{4b}. The above mentioned selective NaBH₄

information about the structure of these molecules. The collision activated of these stable dications, the so called 2E-CAD-MIKE technique led to fragments, characteristic of the indole-indoline skeleton and also of the substituents.

Among the new VLB derivatives, compound 6 showed the most significant cytotoxic activity for LXFL 529 non small cell lung cancer, LXFS 650 small cell lung cancer and OVXF 899 ovarian cancer *in vitro* in human tumor xenografts tested by European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer and National Cancer Institute.

reduction of 12 led to the two new hydroxymethyl vindoline derivatives 13 and 14, where fortunately the *N*-formyl group was also reduced or removed. The ferric ion mediated coupling reaction of 13 with catharanthine (10) resulted in the expected dimer 15. But in the case of the *N*-methyl derivative (14), the dimer 16 could be isolated in quite a small amount and the new vindoline dimer 17 was the main product. Recently, an analogous bisvindoline was obtained by the anodic oxidation⁶ of vindoline (11).

The molecular weights and the structures of the compounds studied were confirmed by mass spectrometry using electron ionization (EI) and fast atom bombardment (FAB) ionization and also tandem mass spectrometric (MS/MS) methods. The abundant formation of doubly charged $[M + 2H]^{2+}$ ions, observed in the +FAB spectra of compounds 5 and 6 provided the possibility of getting more

Experimental

Nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian VXR-300 (¹H : 300 MHz) instrument at 30°, chemical shifts being reported relative to δ_{TMS} = 0.00 ppm. The electron ionization (EI), fast atom bombardment (FAB) and tandem mass spectrometric (MS/MS) experiments were performed with a Fisions VG ZAB-2SEQ hybrid tandem mass spectrometer of BEQQ configuration equipped with a liquid secondary ion source (Cs⁺ ion gun used at 30 keV) and a second field free region collision cell. The collision activated dissociation (CAD) experiments were carried out using argon as collision gas. The samples were dissolved in MeOH and mixed with *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol matrix before subjected to FAB-MS and MS/MS analysis.

3-De(methoxycarbonyl)-4'-deoxy-3',4'-epoxy-3-hydroxymethylvinblastine (4): To anhydrous zinc bromide (5.65 g, 25.1 mmol) in freshly distilled 1,2-dimethoxyethane (200 ml), sodium borohydride (1.95 g, 51.55 mmol) was added under argon at 0°. The mixture was stirred for 4–5 h. Kieselgel HF (8 g) was then added to the suspension which was stirred for 1 h followed by evaporation. The residue was suspended in THF (60 ml) and leurosine (3; 600 mg, 0.742 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at 40° for 0.5 h and monitored by tlc (Kieselgel 60F₂₅₄, eluant: CHCl₃: EtOAc: EtOH = 3:3:1, $R_{f\text{product}} = 0.3$, $R_{f\text{leurosine}} = 0.4$). After the starting material was used up distilled water (10 ml) was added dropwise to the reaction mixture under cooling. After stirring for 20 min the precipitated material was filtered and washed with THF. The solvent was then evaporated off under vacuum to dryness. The residue was dissolved between chloroform and water. The CHCl₃ extract was dried (Na₂SO₄), filtered and evaporated. The residue was purified on silica gel by column chromatography (eluant: see above). The fractions containing compound 4 were evaporated in vacuum and crystallized (acetone-n-hexane) (247 mg, 0.316 mmol, 42.6%), m.p. 189–200°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1730 (ester C=O), 3430 cm⁻¹ (indole NH); δ (CDCl₃) 0.85 (3H, t, H₃-18), 0.97 (3H, t, H₃-18'), 2.16 (3H, s, COMe), 2.62 (1H, s, H-21), 3.07 (3H, s, NMe), 3.54 (1H, s, H-2), 3.55–3.67 (2H, m, CH₂OH), 3.63 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.83 (3H, s, C(11)-OMe), 5.00 (1H, s, H-17), 5.52 (1H, d, H-15), 5.90 (1H, dd, H-14), 6.20 (1H, s, H-12), 6.59 (1H, s, H-9), 7.52 (1H, d, H-9'), 7.98 (1H, s, NH), 9.18 (1H, br s, C(16)-OH); m/z (%) 780 (M⁺, 13), 720 (14), 649 (85), 313 (29), 264 (27), 236 (58), 194 (36), 152 (36), 135 (37), 121 (100), 106 (85).

O⁴-Deacetyl-3-de(methoxycarbonyl)-4'-deoxy-3',4'-epoxy-3-hydroxymethylvinblastine (5): It was prepared in a similar way as described above apart from the fact that the starting material leurosine (3) was refluxed with zinc borohydride supported on silica gel in dry THF for 2 h. After the usual workup and column chromatography 4 (23 mg) was isolated. Continuing the chromatography, the fractions containing 5 were evaporated and crystallized (acetone-n-hexane) to give 5 (248 mg, 0.318 mmol, 42.85%), m.p. 203–10°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{20} + 131.05^\circ$ ($c = 1$ CHCl₃); ν_{max} (KBr) 1735 (ester C=O), 3430 cm⁻¹ (indole NH); δ (CDCl₃) 0.94 (3H, t, H₃-18), 0.97 (3H, t, H₃-18'), 2.52 (1H, s, H-21), 3.07 (3H, s, NMe), 3.52 (2H, s, H-2 and H-17), 3.62 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.72 (1H, d, CH_xOH), 3.83 (3H, s, C(11)-OMe), 3.92 (1H, d, CH_yOH), 5.68 (1H, d, H-15), 5.86 (1H, dd, H-14), 6.17 (1H, s, H-12), 6.58 (1H, s, H-9), 7.51 (1H, d, H-9'), 7.97 (1H, s, NH), 8.87 (1H, br s, C(16)-OH); m/z (%) 739 (MH⁺, 70), 447 (15), 370 ((M + 2H)²⁺, 10).

O⁴-Deacetyl-3-de(methoxycarbonyl)-3-hydroxymethylvinblastine (6): Methanol (1.5 ml) was added dropwise

over a period of 3 h to a boiling mixture of vinblastine sulfate (200 mg, 0.247 mmol) and sodium borohydride (176 mg, 4.65 mmol) in t-BuOH (3.1 ml). The reaction was monitored by tlc (Kieselgel 60 F₂₅₄, eluant: toluene: CHCl₃: MeOH = 8:4:2). After the starting material was used up the reaction mixture was cooled, treated with water (20 ml), and extracted with CHCl₃ (3 × 50 ml). The CHCl₃ extract was dried (Na₂SO₄) and evaporated. The residue was column chromatographed on Kieselgel 60 (0.063–0.200) using the above mentioned eluant. Deacetylvinblastine (21 mg, 0.027 mmol, 11.0%) was isolated as a by-product. Continuing the column chromatography, the resultant product 6 was crystallized from acetone-n-hexane-diethylether mixture (115 mg, 0.155 mmol, 62.8%), m.p. 200–01°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{20} + 102.93^\circ$ ($c = 1$ CHCl₃); ν_{max} (KBr) 1720 cm⁻¹ (ester C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 0.90 (3H, t) and 0.92 (3H, t) [H₃-18,18'], 2.55 (1H, s, H-21), 3.04 (3H, s, NMe), 3.49 (1H, s, H-2), 3.52 (1H, s, H-17), 3.60 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.72 (1H, d, CH_xOH), 3.78 (3H, s, C(11)-OMe), 3.93 (1H, d, CH_yOH), 3.98 (1H, dd, H_x-17'), 5.67 (1H, d, H-15), 5.86 (1H, dd, H-14), 6.15 (1H, s, H-12), 6.62 (1H, s, H-9), 7.53 (1H, d, H-9'), 8.03 (1H, s, NH), 8.89 (1H, br s, C(16)-OH); m/z (%) 741 (MH⁺, 100), 371 (M + 2H)²⁺ (44), 286 (84), 246 (80), 232 (83).

O⁴-Deacetoxy-3-de(methoxycarbonyl)-3-hydroxymethylvinblastine (9): Using a procedure similar to that described for the preparation of 6, compound 8 (2000 mg, 2.656 mmol) was reduced with NaBH₄ in t-BuOH/MeOH. The usual workup and column chromatography (eluant: toluene: CHCl₃: MeOH = 8:4:3) gave 8 (547 mg, 0.755 mmol, 28.42%) which was crystallized from diethyl ether, m.p. 210°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{20} + 93.6^\circ$ ($c = 1$ CHCl₃); ν_{max} (KBr) 1730 cm⁻¹ (ester C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 0.89 (3H, t) and 0.90 (3H, t) [H₃-18,18'], 2.49 (1H, s, H-21), 3.00 (3H, s, NMe), 3.36 (1H, s, H-2), 3.59 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.61 (1H, d, CH_xOH), 3.68 (1H, d, CH_yOH), 3.79 (3H, s, C(11)-OMe), 3.98 (1H, dd, H_x-17'), 5.48 (1H, d, H-15), 5.70 (1H, dd, H-14), 6.12 (1H, s, H-12), 6.61 (1H, s, H-9), 7.53 (1H, d, H-9'), 8.03 (1H, s, NH), 8.98 (1H, br s, C(16)-OH); m/z (%) 725 (MH⁺, 100), 651 (6.3), 571 (5.2), 355 (4.4), 353 (5.3), 196 (13).

3,6-Epoxi-4β-hydroxy-3α-(hydroxymethyl)-16-methoxy-8-oxoaspidospermidine (13) and 3,6-epoxi-4β-hydroxy-3α-(hydroxymethyl)-1-methyl-16-methoxy-8-oxoaspidospermidine (14): 4β-Acetoxy-3,6-epoxi-1-formyl-16-methoxy-3α-(methoxycarbonyl)-8-oxo-aspidospermidin (12; 484 mg, 1.00 mmol) was reduced by NaBH₄ in t-BuOH/MeOH in a similar way as described above. After the usual workup and column chromatography, 14 (41 mg, 0.13 mmol, 10.3%) was isolated and crystallized from diethyl ether, m.p. 213–16°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{20} + 33.3^\circ$ ($c = 0.5$ CHCl₃); ν_{max} (KBr) 1620 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O); m/z (%) 400 (M⁺, 55), 188 (100), 187 (88), 174 (30), 173 (9.2). Continuing the chro-

matography, **13** was isolated as the main product (127 mg, 0.3295 mmol, 32.95%) and crystallized from diethyl ether, m.p. 250–60°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1620 cm^{-1} (amide C=O); **13** δ (DMSO- d_6) 0.82 (3H, t, H₃-18), 1.29 (1H, dq, H_x-19), 1.48 (1H, dq, H_y-19), 1.73 (1H, m, H_x-6), 1.97 (1H, m, H_y-6), 2.33 (1H, dd, H_x-14), 2.39 (1H, dd, H_y-14), 3.04 (1H, m, H_x-5), 3.56 (1H, s, H-2), 3.57 (1H, d, CH_x-OH), 3.64 (3H, s, C(11)-OMe), 3.75 (1H, dd, CH₂OH), 3.80 (1H, d, H-17), 3.90 (1H, s, H-21), 4.07 (1H, t, H-15), 4.14 (1H, m, H_y-5), 4.52 (1H, br, CH₂OH), 5.02 (1H, d, C(17)-OH), 5.78 (1H, s, NH), 6.07 (1H, dd, H-10), 6.09 (1H, d, H-12), 7.02 (1H, d, H-9); **14** δ (CDCl₃) 0.93 (3H, t, H₃-18), 1.35 (1H, dq, H_x-19), 1.70 (1H, m, H_y-19), 1.88–2.08 (2H, m, H₂-6), 2.41 (1H, dd, H_x-14), 2.68 (1H, dd, H_y-14), 2.99 (3H, s, NMe), 3.50 (1H, m, H_x-5), 3.33 (1H, s, H-2), 3.76 (1H, d, CH_xOH), 3.78 (3H, s, C(11)-OMe), 3.95 (1H, d, H-17), 4.02 (1H, d, CH₂OH), 4.10 (1H, s, H-21), 4.10 (1H, t, H-15), 4.34 (1H, m, H_y-5), 6.05 (1H, d, H-12), 6.28 (1H, dd, H-10), 6.88 (1H, d, H-9); **13** m/z (%) 386 (M⁺, 47), 174 (100), 173 (27), 160 (7.2), 159 (3.1).

*O*⁴-Deacetyl-3-de(methoxycarbonyl)-N-demethyl-4'-deoxy-3,6-epoxy-3-(hydroxymethyl)-8-oxovincalcaleukoblastine (**15**): Catharanthine **10** hydrogen sulfate (260 mg, 0.6 mmol) and ferric chloride (810 mg, 3 mmol) were combined in a mixture of glycine buffer (15 ml, containing 7.505 g of glycine and 5.805 g of NaCl in 1 dm⁻³ of water) and HCl (15 ml, 0.1 N) under argon atmosphere. To it **13** (232 mg, 0.6 mmol) was added. After stirring for 3 h at room temperature the suspension became homogeneous. The reaction was controlled by tlc (Kieselgel 60F₂₅₄; eluant, toluene : acetone : MeOH : cc. NH₄OH = 138 : 49 : 10 : 2.5; catharanthine R_f = 0.7, **13** R_f = 0.2). Sodium borohydride (1.2 g, 30 mmol) was then added in small portions. Then cc. NH₄OH was added dropwise (pH 11). The reaction mixture was extracted with dichloromethane (2 × 30 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄), and the solvent evaporated. The residue was purified on a Kieselgel 60 (0.063–0.200) column using the above mentioned eluant to give **15** (84 mg, 0.116 mmol, 19.36%). The crude oil was crystallized from a diethyl ether-acetone solvent mixture, m.p. >260°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1605 (amide C=O), 1722 cm^{-1} (ester C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 1.04 (3H, t) and 1.07 (3H, t) (H₃-18,18'), 2.37 (1H, d, H_x-14), 2.62 (1H, dd, H_y-14), 3.64 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.72 (3H, s, C(11)-OMe), 4.81 (1H, s, CH₂OH), 5.50 (1H, d, C(17)-

OH), 5.70 (1H, dd, H-14), 6.22 (1H, s, H-12), 6.46 (1H, s, H-9), 7.63 (1H, d, H-9'), 8.28 (1H, s, NH); m/z (%) 723 (MH⁺, 100), 663 (10).

*O*⁴-Deacetyl-3-de(methoxycarbonyl)-4'-deoxy-3,6-epoxy-3-(hydroxymethyl)-8-oxovincalcaleukoblastine (**16**) and 15,15-bis[3,6-epoxy-4 β -hydroxy-3 α -(hydroxymethyl)-1-methyl-16-methoxy-8-oxoaspidospermidine] (**17**): Starting from catharanthine **10** hydrogen sulfate (316 mg, 1.337 mmol), the reaction was carried out in a similar way as described in the case of **15** apart from the fact that instead of **13**, compound **14** (469 mg, 1.174 mmol) was added to the reaction mixture. After the usual workup and chromatography, **16** (8 mg, 0.010 mmol) was gained, ν_{\max} (KBr) 1620 (amide C=O), 1725 (ester C=O), 3430 cm^{-1} (indole NH); m/z (%) 737 (MH⁺, 100), 677 (9.2). Continuing the chromatography, **17** (63 mg, 0.158 mmol, 26.92%) was isolated as the main product. The crude oil was crystallized from diethyl ether, m.p. >260°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1633 cm^{-1} (amide C=O); δ (DMSO- d_6) 0.85 (3H, t, H₃-18), 1.29 (1H, dq, H_x-19), 1.52 (1H, dq, H_y-19), 1.72–1.94 (2H, m, H₂-6), 2.34 (1H, dd, H_x-14), 2.40 (1H, dd, H_y-14), 2.95 (1H, m, H_x-5), 3.04 (3H, s, NMe), 3.38 (1H, s, H-2), 3.55–3.72 (2H, d m, CH₂OH), 3.63 (3H, s, C(11)-OMe), 3.87 (1H, d, H-17), 3.94 (1H, s, H-21), 4.10 (1H, t, H-15), 4.13 (1H, m, H_y-5), 4.60 (1H, br, CH₂OH), 5.11 (1H, d, C(17)-OH), 6.20 (1H, s, H-12), 6.62 (1H, s, H-9); m/z (%) 799 (MH⁺, 80), 789 (10).

References

1. "The Alkaloids", eds. A. BROSSI and M. SUFFNESS, Academic, New York, 1990, Vol. 37
2. B. C. RANU and A. R. DAS, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1990, 1334.
3. S. B. MANDAL, V. S. GIN, and S. C. PAKRASH, *Synthesis*, 1987, 1128
4. (a) J. VUKOVIC, A. F. GOODBODY, J. P. KUTNEY, and M. MISAWA, *Tetrahedron*, 1988, **44**, 325; (b) N. LANGLOIS, F. GUERITTE, Y. LANGLOIS, and P. POTIER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 7017
5. H. BÖLCSKEI, E. GÁCS-BAITZ, and Cs. SZÁNTAY, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1989, **51**, 7245.
6. I. TABAKOVIC and K. TABAKOVIC, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1996, **37**, 3659